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BRIDGES 5.0 – Bridging the Way of Industry 4.0 to Industry 5.0¹

1. Keywords

Industry 5.0, social innovation, human-centricity, democratization of economy, skills

2. Research question

The question of participation of affected stakeholders in processes of change, learning and innovation is central in social science theory and application-oriented labour research. Against this backdrop, social innovations can be generated, analysed and shaped at different levels (local, regional, national). Against this background social innovations in the world of work can be viewed with a narrow or broad focus. The narrow focus identifies social innovations on company level (e.g., corporate concepts, organisational forms, management approaches, methods of introduction technology and technological infrastructures, and skills development). With a slightly broader focus, attention is directed to practices of cooperation with relevant suppliers or to the design of customer relationships. If you open the focus wide interest is shifting to interactions with relevant environmental factors of the companies. The attention then is on legal framework conditions, political requirements and negotiation processes between and with players of different policy areas (e.g., labour, industrial, technology, innovation, education and regional policy). Who are relevant actors (e.g. workers, managers, trade unionists, politicians, civil society) depends on the adjustment of the zoom. A comprehensive approach of social innovations in this context requires to understand operational developments in their interaction with external actors. Against this background, we want to classify the debate on the EU concept of Industry 5.0 and ask under which perspectives (narrower and wider zoom) it is being driven forward and to what extent a comprehensive approach can be outlined.

3. Methods

Following on from the originally German concept of Industry 4.0, the European Union (EU) has introduced the concept of Industry 5.0 and is thereby driving its development with a particular emphasis on the aspects human-centricity, sustainability and resilience [1,2].

The central debate is characterized by a narrow focus on company operations and revolves around questions of skills and how to operationalise the way from a technology to a human-centric paradigm. Based on own research results we want to summarize the state of art in section 4.1. This is based on results of the BRIDGES 5.0 project (<https://bridges5-0.eu/>) and takes up some already conducted efforts of companies on their way to a more human-centric innovation and implementation of new technologies. The results based on workshop and survey results showing the perspective of the concerned managers and workforce. Included are also findings based on a narrative literature review. Furthermore, we elaborate in section 4.2 impulses from Industry 5.0 to widen the focus. Companies should overcome maximizing profit and foster to develop solutions to major societal, in particular socio-ecological,

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challenges. As to be shown the EU's ambition requires not only greater opportunities for employees but also for regional and especially civil society actors to influence strategic corporate decisions and developments. We sketch some methods and in section 4.3 we suggest a comprehensive model (ecosystem). In section 5 we end with a short conclusion. 4.2 and 4.3 are also based on a literature analysis in context of the BRIDGES 5.0 project.

4. Results

4.1 Narrow focus: *The skill debate*

Industry 4.0 and 5.0 have a lot in common. But they differ fundamentally in their understanding of ends and means:

- 4.0: Human centricity must be reconciled with technology and profit-oriented requirements
- 5.0: Technology and profit-oriented thinking must be reconciled with human centricity.

In this regard it is crucial that the people (stakeholders, workers, civil society) have the right skills to enable digital, green, and social transitions. With regard to skills in a transforming industry the EU-Industry 5.0 concept paper names two central problems: Firstly, that *"skills needs are evolving as fast as technologies"* and that European industries cannot meet these needs; and secondly, that *"young people do not feel adequately equipped with the skills needed for the future labour market"* [1, p. 18]. Against this background the core question is: What skills should the workforce of the future have and how can companies, industries and employees detect and fulfil these skill needs more rapidly? A large amount of literature discuss future skill demands alongside the categories of digital, personal, social and methodological skills.

Industry 5.0 intends to foster the significance of workers in the digital transformation. The idea is to design tasks and the required skills in a way that they enable an improvement in all relevant dimensions (e.g., health, safety, autonomy, range of tasks), if possible in an individualized form. The digital transformation should be seen as an enabler. It is assumed that it is specifically the combination of human and technological capacities that create a new quality of opportunities for companies and staff.

Speed is perhaps the most important challenge when it comes to the question how skills should be developed in an Industry 5.0. In this context platform-based skills intelligence tools are of great importance. The challenge is to design the data in a way that it adequately reflects the specific circumstances of skill decisions, be in a region, a company or for (regional or local) stakeholders. This specialisation is prerequisite for a profitable use of data. For example, the following questions should be considered when designing tools with an industry reference:

- Which categories of skills should be used?
- What are the target groups?
- At which geographical levels do they operate?
- What decision do they need to make?
- What data do they need to make this decision (demand and supply information)?
- How can this data be provided (expert-driven or digital technologies driven)?

Especially Bridges 5.0 is bridging the transformation from Industry 4.0 to Industry 5.0 by workforce and approaches like Teaching and Learning Factories. Additionally, the European Commission has launched a Community of Practice Industry 5.0 which developed a Learning and Assessment Tool. The new Skills Alliance for the Green, Digital and Social Transformation of the Energy Intensive Industries (Skills4EII) under the Pact for Skills will explicitly develop skills for Industry 5.0 in the energy intensive industry (2025-2028). The energy intensive industries related skills alliances ESSA, SPIRE-SAIS, and Skills4EII underline the growing importance of online training platforms with a digital individual learning assessment, skills gap analysis and related tailor-made online training modules (steelHub, SKILLS4Planet, and the upcoming HUB5.0).

4.2 Wide focus: Aligning entrepreneurial and social objectives

Industry 5.0 subordinates the profit demands of shareholders to the common good of citizens. The paper by Breque et al. [1] and, in particular, the related paper by the ESIR-expert-group [2] contain a number of programmatic statements that imply substantial changes in the social and economic system. This broader understanding of the purpose of industrial production and particularly the focus on stakeholders instead of shareholders interest (*stakeholder capitalism*) leads to approaches addressing a broader range of those stakeholders in factories and beyond. Industry 5.0 intends to put companies much more strongly at the service of solving social problems. This engagement cannot be achieved solely through top-down specifications in the form of compliance with legal requirements, but requires adequate multi-stakeholder negotiation processes based on (as yet largely absent) forms of governance, dialog instruments and practices including also civil society.

Banholzer therefore considers it a precarious endeavour that Industry 5.0 was launched with a top-down impulse from the executives "*without outlining a concept of the public sphere, political discourse or deliberative, agonal or pragmatist debate in pluralist democracies*" [3, p. 39]. The EU-concept of Industry 5.0 mentions at least fundamentally suitable approaches such as corporate social responsibility and shared value. But they are currently highly inadequate to realize the intention of Industry 5.0. For this they would have to be developed significantly further. This also applies to more far-reaching approaches such as doughnut economy, economy for common good and transformation networks. The latter refers to a very recent approach bringing together different regional actors in transformation networks. The idea is to include the main stakeholders in a region because they play a crucial role in shaping local economic and labour policies and possess the required expertise. These stakeholders include employer associations or major influential companies, trade unions and works councils, employment agencies, state and local authorities, universities and research institutions, and civil society representatives.

Considering that many articles highlight the significance of multi-level actor interaction and coordination in tackling directionality and other transformative challenges, it is somewhat surprising that there are relatively few analyses examining the specific roles and contributions of different actors in addressing these challenges. However, the 5.0-ambition is confronted with a general lack of such tried-and-tested concepts and corresponding experiences provided by research.

4.3 Integrating entrepreneurial and social objectives in a multidimensional social innovation ecosystem

Industry 5.0 opens up a claim to democratisation and participation that goes beyond company boundaries and extends to questioning traditional capitalist orientations. This requires embedding and linking company design projects in specific forms of mission-orientated innovation policy and governance. Combining organizational actors with regional actors (civil society) results in the model of a multidimensional innovation ecosystem driven by civil society.

Fig. 1. Industry 5.0 as a multidimensional innovation ecosystem, own depiction

Industry 5.0 (Smart Factory) appears here embedded in a comprehensive innovation ecosystem. The boundaries of the *Smart Factory* are open to society insofar as opportunities are sought to realise the Societal Development Goals. The exchange and negotiation processes between *society* and companies must be underpinned by the development of new forms and instruments of co-evolutionary and co-creative learning and development. The shift from shareholder value to stakeholder value intends to be combined with the demand that companies subordinate their profit interests to the interests of employees and society. This requires a significant increase in interactivity and co-evolution with regional players in which the active involvement of *civil society* is of particular importance. The necessary deliberative negotiation, implementation and coordination mechanisms and instruments have yet to be developed. Starting points for this involvement can be found in approaches from corporate social responsibility, shared value, economy of common good or transformation councils and networks. The co-evolutionary relationship between the enterprise and society should be aligned by the specific *mission* of Industry 5.0. It is not only to become more human-centric, sustainable and resilient but also to overcome neoliberal and traditionally capitalist economic models. But in its current form, the mission remains primarily focussed on the SDG-targets. And the mission of Industry 5.0 is vaulted over by a general *mission-oriented transformative innovation policy*.

5. Conclusions

The EU's Industry 5.0 concept aims to empower workers and civil society by focusing both on skill-based human-centric approaches at the enterprise level and on businesses' responsibility to address societal issues.

Current debates mainly centre on the company, emphasizing socio-technical perspectives on technology-worker interactions. Early findings suggest that non-technological factors, like skill development, are key to Industry 5.0's transformation.

Although some approaches consider the company-society relationship, there's a lack of conceptual frameworks and methods for engaging regional and societal actors. Dialogue competency development is underexplored, and empirical examples are rare.

The development of suitable structures for coordination, governance, and skills development has just begun. Key issues include clarifying the roles of regional players, empowering and implementation.

A comprehensive framework is needed to guide stakeholders and companies toward Industry 5.0. We propose a multidimensional innovation ecosystem as a possible solution.

References

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